

INCREASING TEACHER'S INFLUENCE IN EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER CONDITIONS - AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

¹Khimmataliev Dustnazar Omonovich, ²Rasulov Akbar Namozovich

¹Doctor of pedagogic sciences, professor

²Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor
Chirchik State Pedagogical University

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Abstract. Any innovation in the field of education is represented by the creation, acquisition, use and distribution of new things. Also, innovations in education include the introduction of modern ideas and the introduction of testing foundations and methods into the educational process, significantly changing and improving their quality.

The article highlights the highest level of professional activity of the teacher in the conditions of the educational cluster, that is, the introduction of pedagogical innovations.

Keywords: quality, activity, innovation, authority, knowledge, skill, goal, problem, education, system, research.

Introduction

The most important trend in the development of education is to increase its quality, as well as to recognize the need for continuity of "lifelong" learning. Modern education reform puts new demands on pedagogues. Today, there is a great need for a teacher who can master the technologies that ensure the individualization of education, the achievement of planned results, and constantly tries to improve his skills. Therefore, the main direction of this direction is the idea: when teaching children, the teacher must know how to learn.

In the state educational standards, it becomes urgent to constantly improve the professional level of pedagogues, that is, to create a system to ensure its prestige increases.

The idea of creating educational clusters is not accidental. An educational cluster is an organizational form of combining the efforts of interested parties to achieve certain advantages in the educational system, and in this form, the professional growth of the teacher is more effective. The clustering approach has been defined differently in studies of educational clustering. In particular, T.I.Shamova describes a cluster as a separate field (education, economy, etc.) and calls it a mechanism for strengthening the organizational forms of the union of fields interested in achieving competitive efficiency [4].

And L. Bespalova defines it as a structure consisting of several equal parts that preserves its full functional workability among optional components [1].

L. I. Osechkina interprets it as a means of forming support for innovations in the education-science-production system [3].

In order to increase the authority of the teacher in the conditions of the educational cluster, it is necessary to solve the following main tasks:

- creating conditions for the successful activity of each teacher in the organization of educational activities based on the requirements of the state educational standard;
- creating conditions for the involvement of every teacher in innovative activities;
- creating conditions for each teacher to effectively use modern educational technologies, including design and research;

- creating conditions for the development and implementation of individual programs for personal continuous professional growth and portfolio formation by teachers.

Method

In the conditions of the educational cluster, it is possible to increase the authority of the teacher in 5 directions:

1. Professional cooperation.

The main idea: "Educate yourself by teaching others." This will be helped by interactive pedagogical councils, scientific-practical seminars, skill schools, open classes, organization of methodical days of "experience sharing", creating a bank of training programs within the cluster in subjects, training courses, lessons, master classes, etc.

2. Skill school.

Main idea: "Help me learn because you know how." In this, a program of support for newly employed teachers is implemented, which includes the organization of mentoring, development of individual training programs for each young specialist, holding educational seminars, mutual participation in classes, etc.

3. Perfection.

The main idea: "New school - new teacher". This includes teachers' mastering of innovative technologies, methodical seminars, pedagogical councils, methodical practical training, master classes, open classes using innovative technologies, keeping teachers' personal websites and blogs, posting materials on the school's website, creating a school methodical bank, etc. did not help.

4. Professional creativity.

The main idea: "From pedagogical skills to professional prestige". This is helped by participation of teachers in professional competitions of various levels, participation in forums, seminars, conferences, development of competition projects for foundation and grant programs, publication of materials summarizing experience, etc.

5. Self-professional development.

The main idea: "There is no limit to perfection." This includes the preparation of courses, continuous replenishment of the teacher's portfolio, development of personal professional growth programs, participation of teachers in professional communities, associations, self-education through participation in webinars and other forms of distance education, generalization of experience, publications, work experience, etc.

The organization of educational cluster work is effective in increasing the influence of teachers, and the cluster is an excellent tool for overcoming the isolation and inertia of teachers. Mutual and self-development of its subjects takes place within the cluster. Interactions within the cluster create completely new possibilities, new creative combinations.

Results and discussion

Increasing the authority of the teacher in the conditions of the educational cluster allows them to acquire knowledge, skills, to optimally realize their goals, to choose methods of activity that allow them to solve the problems they face in education. Also, it is possible to have an active influence on the education, upbringing, development, socialization of students, and at the same time to become a mobile teacher with competitive, systematic and methodical thinking.

Based on this, the authority of the teacher is understood in two ways:

1. In the vertical sense - the teacher climbs up the ladder of authority.

2. In the horizontal sense - the authority of the teacher implies the continuous development and improvement of professional skills without changing the hierarchy of official positions.

It is believed that vertical and horizontal influence are different areas of professional life, different ways of performing professional activities.

Although these are two different career paths to prestige, what they have in common comes with professional self-organization, independence, belonging, and a sense of tenure.

A horizontal teaching reputation is developed by meeting the following criteria:

- Management's opinion about the potential and opportunities of the teacher.
- The teacher must have the necessary external characteristics that have a positive effect on professional influence (evaluated scientific and research activities, services, etc.).
- Adequate assessment of one's professional skills and abilities, comparing them with professional and labor requirements.
- Creative professional activity.
- Reflecting on one's pedagogical activity.

Necessary conditions for successfully increasing the authority of a teacher:

1. Promotion of teaching staff by the leaders of the educational cluster.
2. Providing professional help and support to young teachers.
3. Recognition of pedagogical services of each person for the whole community.

Recently, great importance has been attached to teachers who decide to engage in scientific research and at the same time continue practical work with children in educational institutions. The number of such teachers is relatively small, but their desire to grow and improve their skills is high.

Professional growth of a teacher is a process of development, integration and implementation of professional important personal qualities, consisting of abilities, professional knowledge and skills, high functional quality, change of the inner world of the teacher, which ultimately leads to the construction of a new way of life consciously.

The teacher himself, as well as his expectations and existing ideas about the professional future, are important in professional growth. Successful professional prestige career growth depends on personal motives, motivation and development of a person.

Summary

Climbing the career ladder, vertical and horizontal promotion in the context of the educational cluster instills respect for the teacher. The authority of the teacher rises up the hierarchical ladder, for another it is an opportunity for creative self-expression and professional excellence.

Pedagogical professionalism is the basis of pedagogical activity, without which children cannot be taught at school. Pedagogical skills are based on the necessary theoretical and practical training of teachers, which is given in pedagogical educational institutions and continues to be improved in the course of professional activity.

Pedagogical skill - a quality indicator of the teacher's pedagogical activity, that is, pedagogical and professional skills lead to the highest level of excellence/

Pedagogical creativity includes specific components of innovation, but often this innovation is not related to the promotion of new ideas and foundations of learning and teaching, but to changing the methods of educational work, their specific modernization.

The highest level of a teacher's professional activity is pedagogical innovation. It involves the introduction of new, modern ideas and the introduction of the foundations and methods of testing into the educational process, significantly changing and improving their quality.

Initially, the term "innovation", widely understood as something new and socially significant, appeared in the middle of the last century in studies of cultural studies and linguistics to describe the processes of cultural diffusion. It was introduced to consider the spread of a phenomenon from one cultural area to another, a situation in which it appeared not as a cultural tradition, but as a cultural (linguistic) innovation that was assimilated in one form or another in the existing culture. This diffusion is, in fact, interpreted as a natural mechanism of cultural development.

The growing interest in the possibilities of using innovative processes in society and the strengthening of their mastery led to the formation of a special field of knowledge - innovation - as a special science about innovations from the beginning of the 20th century, within which the laws of technical innovations in the field of material production began to be studied (W. Secada, C. Taylor, A .A. Toffler, W. Woolf and others).

Innovation has emerged as a reflection of the growing need for various firms to develop and implement these new services and ideas. Since the 1930s, terms such as "firm's innovation policy" and "innovation process" have been used in the United States.

If at first they were interested in innovation, first of all, in the economic and social laws of creation and distribution of scientific and technical innovations, then they spread to the interests of the new field of knowledge and various social innovations, first of all, to innovations in organizations and enterprises (changes in the management structure, new methods of decision-making , mastering new activities, etc.).

The development of pedagogical innovation in our country is primarily related to the emergence and formation of a mass social pedagogical movement. Like any socio-cultural phenomenon, the innovative pedagogical movement has its own subjective and objective conditions for its emergence, its history and the main directions of its formation.

Any innovation in education is relative both from a personal and temporal (historical) point of view. What is new to one teacher may not be new to another. Innovation always has a specific historical character, it is born in a specific period and solves the problems of a specific historical period. An innovation can very quickly become the property of many, enter the practice of mass education, but then it can become obsolete and hinder further development.

It is precisely because of the ambiguity of the term "new" (especially in the field of education) that new publications on this issue constantly appear in the pedagogical literature. Let's look at some of them.

Innovation in pedagogy is not only ideas, approaches, methods and technologies that have not been used before, but also a complex of elements with a progressive beginning that allows effective solving of educational problems in changing conditions and situations. That is, in the interpretation of this author, innovation actually corresponds to the concept of "progressiveness". However, in practice, it is known that innovation does not always correspond to progressiveness and development, even the broader concept of "modernity".

N.R. Yusufbekova, a researcher of the problems of pedagogical innovation, defines innovation as the content of changes in the pedagogical reality that were previously unknown and

did not yet lead to results, which can develop the theory and practice of education. This content can be related to the entire pedagogical reality, as well as to its individual components [5].

Considering the system of basic concepts of pedagogical innovation, N.R. Yusufbekova distinguishes three blocks of the structure of innovative processes in the educational system:

The first block is the block of creating new things in pedagogy. Categories such as innovations in pedagogy, classification of educational innovations, conditions for creation of new ones, criteria of innovation, measure of readiness to master and use new ones, traditions and innovations, stages of creation of new ones in pedagogy are considered here.

The second block is the block of new perception, assimilation and evaluation. In this block, concepts such as pedagogical team, evaluation of innovations, innovation environment, readiness of the pedagogical team to perceive and evaluate new things are introduced.

The third block is the new use and application block. In this block, the rules and types of introduction, use and application of the new are studied [5].

Due to the different interpretations of the term "new" in the field of education, until now there is no generally accepted interpretation of the concept of "educational innovation" in the pedagogical literature and in the innovative educational environment.

Many scientists (similar to N.R. Yusufbekova's research, which identified three blocks in the composition of any innovation in the field of education) give a broader understanding of educational innovation, understanding it as a process of creating, mastering, using and distributing new things. Some researchers dealing with this issue give a more strict definition of educational innovation, by which they understand only the activity of creating new things. The processes of assimilation, use, distribution of the new are not considered by them to be truly innovative.

In the conditions of the educational cluster, increasing the authority of the teacher requires the highest level of his professional activity, that is, introducing pedagogical innovations, introducing and testing new, modern ideas into the educational process, significantly changing and improving the quality of education.

REFERENCES

1. Беспалова Л. Что Такое Кластер? иКБ: <http://siok.rightside.ru/siok/> 2009-12-01-06-24-41. Загл. с экрана.
2. Загвязинский В.И. Инновационные процессы в образовании и педагогическая наука // Инновационные процессы в образовании. - Тюмень, 1990.
3. Осечкина, Л.И. Кластерный подход как условие повышения эффективности деятельности вуза / Л.И. Осечкина // Высшее образование в России. № 8-9, 2012. - С.73-76.
4. Шамова Т.И. Исследовательский подход в управлении школой. М., 1992.
5. Юсуфбекова Н.Р. Общие основы педагогической инноватики. Опыт разработки теории инновационных процессов в образовании. - М., 1991.
6. Taylor C Sources of the self. - Boston : Harvard University Press, 1989.